

PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES THROUGH METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403075>

Abstract. *This article covers such issues as the requirements for the organization of Independent Education of students in educational institutions of training of specialist personnel to future professional educational institutions, their degrees of independence in independent work activities, forms, methods and means of the organization and transfer process of Independent Education, implementation statuses in the auditorium and outside the audience, achievement of.*

Keywords: *independent education, levels of independence, methods, forms, audience, methods of "webquest" and "mind mapping", specialist personnel, educational tools.*

Introduction. In prestigious educational institutions of developed countries in the world, special attention is paid to the implementation of independent education in preparing students for professional activities. Because in today's globalized world, there is a need for specialists who can think independently and who have developed comprehensive thinking. Teaching students to think independently in the educational process is the need of the hour. One of the urgent tasks is to develop students' inclination to study, their abilities, knowledge and skills, to increase their readiness for professional activities, teaching practical subjects, and effectively organizing their independent and creative work. At all stages of higher education, independent thinking should remain a basic requirement for a future professional. Thinking or reasoning is considered to be the highest form of the student's mental activity, intelligence, etiquette, and conscious behavior. From this point of view, professional mobility (academic mobility) and time management (time management) in modeling the independent learning process of learners in educational institutions and the application and implementation of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the educational process remain relevant.

The priorities of the new professional education, which is rapidly developing in our republic, envisage the training of creative specialists who independently organize the methods of professional activity. "Formation of a spiritually rich and comprehensively matured person with an independent outlook and thinking in professional educational institutions" is defined as an urgent task. The quality of professional education and professional training is inextricably linked with the learner's activity in the educational process and the methods of organizing independent education. Therefore, it is important to develop independent work with modern educational and methodological support in the future professional education teacher in the implementation of independent education. In addition, it requires the implementation of innovative educational methods aimed at the development of professional skills based on the expansion of didactic opportunities of independent education of students in educational practices.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PF-5812 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 6, 2019 "On additional measures to further improve the professional education system" Decree No. 466 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 7, 2020 "On the approval of normative legal documents regulating the system of continuous primary, secondary and secondary special professional education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the tasks specified in other normative legal documents related to this activity serves the implementation to a certain extent.

The main part. A number of scientific researches have been conducted by the scientists of our republic and foreign countries on the development of independent education and improvement of preparation for professional activity, and independent education is one of the forms of education aimed at strengthening the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications, and independent study of additional information or material.

Independent work of students (here in after TMI) is a unique educational activity of a student, which is aimed at independent completion of didactic tasks, interest in learning and increasing knowledge in a specific field of science. The content of TMI will be related to the implementation of practical tasks that allow the formation of logical thinking, creative activity, research approach in mastering the educational material.

In students' independent work activities, their independence levels are determined based on 3 different indicators:

1. Self-awareness in a reproductive form (repeating the material, completing tasks, etc.) is the first level of the process of creative learning and mastering.

2. The second level of creative independence is the combination of previously learned and new material. The second stage is characterized by a high level of independence, the selected material is connected and restored with new methods of processing and analyzing the received information.

3. The next, higher level of creative independence is determined by the student's ability to solve tasks, acquire new knowledge and acquire new skills using convenient methods of information search, selection and learning. The highest level of independent education is defined by independent formulation of problems and striving to solve them independently.

The first two levels must be mastered to reach the last level. Creative thinking is also part of the process of acquiring sustainable skills for independent work. Talent is required for the manifestation of creative thinking, the process of acquiring knowledge, studying an interesting problem is related to creativity and thinking, and creative thinking skills are formed.

Summarizing the above considerations, the use of methods of organizing independent education in the preparation of students for professional activities, interactive methods during the transition of lessons, using pedagogical technologies will serve to increase the independence of students, to achieve effective indicators of the process of mastering lessons.

Educational methods. Forms, methods and means of organizing and conducting independent education are implemented in the classroom and outside the classroom. Interactive methods and modern pedagogical technologies are used in its implementation. Textbooks, instructional manuals and information technology tools are used to pass the subject of educational practice.

Several pedagogical processes are implemented in preparing students for professional activities through independent education. Three main processes were used in the research, which are:

- teaching forms (learning practice, independent work), teaching methods (mind mapping, webquest, problem solving activities);
- teaching tools: independent education (textbook, study guide, independent work instructions);
- technical conditions (computer, projector, programs, internet networks).

One of the main motivations for independent learning in oral, visual, and practical methods of educational practice is the desire for something new, unknown, and is associated with external stimulation and internal qualities of a person. The ability to usefully implement the experience gained in the labor market and the ability to think creatively are the main incentives for creative assimilation of knowledge; Another incentive is the need to understand the objective reality more deeply and understand that the knowledge acquired by students is the basis of social, personal and professional development.

Focused on directing the tasks and tasks performed during the lesson to independent learning. Attention was paid to the development of students' independence when passing the science of educational practice through the "webquest" and "mind mapping" method, that is, these components of pedagogical technology and interactive methods were activated in the training of a pedagogue who has his own firm opinion, can find solutions in problem situations, and is an independent seeker.

In pedagogy, webquest means solving problem tasks, working on a project using Internet resources. Webquest promotes the following:

- search for information on the Internet about the assignment given by the teacher to students;
- development of thinking skills of students at the stage of information analysis, summarization and evaluation;
- encourage students to learn independently from teachers;
- development of research and creative abilities of students;
- improve personal self-esteem.

This technology is suitable for the organization of individual or group work, as well as for extracurricular activities.

"Mind mapping" method is one of the teaching methods that explore new, interesting and useful methods. This method is represented by images and colors. This method, which teaches information reception, memorization, and creative thinking when using tables and drawings, is intended to be used in the course of practical tasks.

Conducting lesson processes using various interactive methods for each of them, "Problem solving activities" method during professional training:

- critical analysis of students' activities;
- finding non-standard solutions to identified problems and situations;
- mastering pedagogical innovations and applying them in the educational process;
- modern education provides an opportunity to acquire skills in the use of technologies. In this, the knowledge, skills and competences of innovative pedagogical activity are formed mainly in solving real professional tasks.

Experiment results. The research was conducted on the basis of the methodology intended to direct students to independent education. On the basis of role-playing games, pedagogical problems and exercises, group and small group sessions and individual sessions, conversations, lectures, and seminars were organized. cognitive - level of formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications through independent work; active-reflexive - was determined based on the criteria of self-assessment and development of independent work.

The level of formation and consistent development of independent activity in the respondents was studied and analyzed based on certain criteria. The results obtained from the experimental and control groups were studied, summarized and compared. Based on the results, final conclusions were drawn.

The result of the level of preparation for professional activity among students of the tajpibacinov and nazopat groups was as follows:

in the experimental group, 11.1% of the students achieved the excellent level at the beginning of the experiment, 12.8% of the students achieved the excellent level at the end of the experiment, 11.4% of the students achieved the excellent level at the beginning of the experiment, and 27.7% of the students achieved the excellent level at the end of the experiment. He was in excellent condition;

the number of students who had good grades was 33.2% in the first grade in the control group, 38.3% in the last grade, 32.4% in the experimental group, and 50.5% in the final grade. ;

the number of students with multiple skills at a satisfactory level decreased from 43.7% to 36.2% in the patient group, while it decreased from 42.7% to 15.8% in the experimental group;

the number of students with unsatisfactory performance changed from 12% to 12.7% in the control groups, and decreased from 13.5% to 6% in the experimental groups.

Summary. Summarizing the conducted scientific research, presented methodological developments, recommendations, the following conclusions were reached:

1. Based on the topic of the research, according to the analysis of scientific sources, it can be said that as a result of the development of the characteristics of independence of students in higher education (professional competence, independent activity, quick acceptable decision-making and control of the knowledge system), the degree of creative independence in the educational process (self- understanding, independent analysis and processing of information and creative thinking) are manifested.

2. Organizational-pedagogical conditions (teaching content, time distribution and effectiveness) of independent education in professional subjects were scientifically and methodically justified by stratification of the role of learners in educational practices by means of methods of organizing independent education in higher education institutions.

3. By implementing interactive educational methods such as "webquest", "mind mapping" and "problem solving activities" designed for self-assessment and self-assessment of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students in the process of organizing independent education, future pedagogues-educators the methodology of training for professional activity has been improved.

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